

Mobile Application for Taxi Services in Rural Areas

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

Residents of rural areas often use public transport. Also, there are lots of villages around the main town. Some villages have buses about once an hour. As a result, many locals use three-wheelers for their transport. Also, residents of some villages have to wait for about an hour for a public bus to reach the main towns, or they have to wait for a three-wheel to arrive. Also, villagers want to transport their vegetables or pets, but some three-wheel drivers are not willing to do it. Therefore, I am developing a 'FastTuk' mobile application and came up with a solution in order to find the three-wheel for villagers based on their purpose.

Overview of the Existing System

How the existing system functions:

Many taxi services are situated in Sri Lanka in the existing system, and these companies mainly focus on urban areas. Also, the services are categorized by using vehicle types. And not have any mobile taxi applications for rural areas. Also, it did not categorize by using people's needs.

Problems with Existing System:

Existing systems haven't been categorized by using people's needs. Also, most taxi services are situated in urban areas, not rural ones. Therefore, some people who live in rural areas are not familiar with fully functional and complex taxi service mobile applications.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

The problem with the system is that people in many rural areas use public transportation. But it is limited, and sometimes a huge time gap is there in between. Some villages have buses about once an hour. As a result, many locals use three-wheelers for their transportation purposes. And also, you have to wait for a three-wheel to arrive. And most people who live in rural areas are farmers, and they want to transport their vegetables to the central city, but sometimes they cannot find the exact three-wheel driver who is willing to transport vegetables to the main town. And also, some people want to transport their pets to the veterinary doctor or elsewhere but cannot use public transportation. Finding three wheels to transport pets is also challenging because some drivers do not allow you to bring your pet in their vehicle.

Issues Identified

- Difficult to find three-wheel for travel as they need.
- Difficult to find a three-wheel drive who is willing to transport vegetables and pets.

Requirement analysis

Functional Requirements

Functional requirements are considered the main features that should be offered by a system to carry out its operations effectively. These functional requirements are identified as related to inputs, processes, outputs, and database operations of the system, which are required to satisfy clients' requirements. Users and drivers can input their details also, and the driver can input the willing types of transport. Users can easily find available drivers. They need to just click the type of transportation, and they can find the willing driver for their purpose.

Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements increase user experience to the user and deliver a better service through the system. The application should be user-friendly, where any user should be able to easily understand how to use the system.

System Diagram

Figure 1: System diagram customer side

Figure 2: System diagram for driver side

When discussing the above diagram, users and drivers can **sign up** and **register** separately. If they have already signed up, they can **sign in** easily.

When it comes to the customer side in **Dashboard**, they can select the type of ride (vegetable, pet or passenger). And once tap on the type, the customer will navigate to **the available drivers' details screen**. Here, users can directly contact drivers within 1km.

When it comes to the driver side in **Dashboard**, the driver can update their willingness types and set their status as online or offline.

System Development

Development Methodology used:

This project used the Agile methodology to produce a high-quality product while considering client needs and releasing a usable component after each sprint.

Technologies used:

Flutter framework and dart language are used when developing the mobile application. Visual studio code: the IDE to develop the mobile application also used the Firebase cloud firestore database to store the data.

Conclusion

This mobile taxi application, named “FastTuk” was developed for people in rural areas. The main purpose of this application is to allow people to find a taxi based on their needs. Using this mobile application, people can easily find a taxi for their needs. This application divided people’s needs into three categories passengers’ vegetables, and pets. They can contact the drivers with only one click. Also, drivers can easily choose their willingness types of transport, and they can set whether they are online or not.

References

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